

Terrestrial photography applications on the snow cover: developing a data service for monitoring extreme events in Svalbard (PASSES 3)

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1. Introduction

The availability of Earth Observation (EO) data in remote areas poses a critical challenge that affects our ability to comprehensively describe processes occurring in the Arctic. Fortunately, satellite data have become increasingly accessible in regions like Svalbard, thanks to new missions supported by international and national space agencies. However, in-situ observations in the Arctic demand substantial logistical efforts, highlighting the need for an intermediary layer of observations to bridge the gap between these distinct data sources (Salzano et al. 2021b). Ensuring temporal alignment between satellite overpasses and field-based campaigns is a primary task, one that can be resolved by deploying automated stations with higher temporal resolution compared to spaceborne or airborne platforms. The COVID-19 pandemic also underscored the importance of having backup solutions in case of disruptions to fieldwork (Jawak et al. 2021). In line

with these considerations, SIOS has supported the transition from a survey focused on terrestrial photography applications (Salzano et al. 2021a) to a time-lapse camera network specifically designed for cryospheric studies, particularly snow cover monitoring. Building upon the recommendations of the PASSES initiative, the SIOS Snow Pilot project played a vital role in establishing a time-lapse camera network in Svalbard, following the guidelines outlined in Salzano et al. (2022). This update chapter encompasses several key elements: an updated survey of terrestrial applications for snow cover monitoring, the conceptual framework of the service associated with the time-lapse camera network, and the potential synergies offered by time-lapse cameras in describing the snow melting process during the snow season, in conjunction with satellite and in-situ observations.

2. Moving from single applications to an integrated data service

2.1. The updated survey

Analysing published papers that employ time-lapse cameras in Svalbard provides valuable statistics for comprehending the evolution of applications and technologies in remote regions. The results presented in this survey were obtained using the same methodology as defined in Salzano et al. (2022). To gather these scientific publications, we employed the Scopus platform and used the query string “(time-lapse OR camera OR photography OR webcam) AND Svalbard” to search within paper titles, abstracts, and keywords. As of 31 August 2023, we identified a total of 186 articles (the list is available online (Salzano et al. 2023), with institutes from Norway, the United Kingdom, France, Italy, Sweden, the United States, and Poland being the

most prominently represented. The observed trend exhibits growth, doubling every ten years, with two significant increments occurring in 2007 and 2019. The initial surge in publications can be attributed to the widespread adoption of digital cameras over film devices. The second notable increase may be attributed to the development of smart CMOS sensor modules, the growing utilization of IoT solutions, and potentially the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. This observed pattern aligns with the broader trend of more publications on the application of time-lapse cameras for monitoring snow cover. Overall, the numbers are notably higher, as the applications extend far beyond the scope of Svalbard, encompassing a diverse range of research areas.

2.2. Establishing a time-lapse camera network in Svalbard.

The PASSES initiative is a success story, demonstrating how individual applications, backed by various national institutions, came together to shape a shared protocol, and collaborate on establishing a regional sensor network under the auspices of SIOS (Figure 1). The consortium behind the Snow Pilot project, with support from SIOS, used the knowledge and recommendations outlined in the SESS reports (Salzano et al. 2021a; 2022) as a starting point. The development of the time-lapse camera network entailed diverse contributions, including establishing necessary infrastructure, designing a streamlined data processing chain, and conceptualizing the service itself. The first component involved identifying architectural nodes and optimizing existing observing facilities.

Three sites were selected based on the survey of existing applications and those facilities were integrated to increase the observing capacities and to fill the identified gaps. The network will cover an ideal N-S transect across Svalbard (Figure 2) with large flat areas easily recognizable by satellite platforms (Ny-Ålesund, Adventdalen and Hornsund).

The optimisation of the network in Ny-Ålesund will be finalised in 2024 by adding a new camera system to enhance coverage over the Bayelva catchment, which is already partially covered by sensors operated by the Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) and the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) at the Amundsen-Nobile Climate Change Tower. Furthermore, the network will expand to year-round coverage of Adventdalen, where monitoring will involve installing a device within a UNIS facility

Figure 1: Locations of all current cameras in the network as identified by the survey in 2023. In addition, new cameras installed through two recent projects, the SIOS snow pilot¹ and CRIOS².

¹ <https://sios-svalbard.org/SnowPilot2022>

² <https://crios.pl/>

with support from NPI. Lastly, the Hornsund area will complete the transect, featuring a redesigned asset operated by the Institute of Geophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IG PAS). The logistics for these installations is an ongoing challenge, complicated by permitting and safety issues that we aim to resolve soon. While the Snow Pilot project contributed the network's most advanced hardware (three Harbotronics Cyclapse systems with the 24.2-megapixel sensor resolution), data processing has been designed to manage a wide range of image formats. The designed infrastructure will be the backbone of an additional Cryosphere Integrated Observation Network on Svalbard (CRIOS) that will be operational in 2024.

Designing the data processing chain necessitated an analysis of various tasks, with a focus on identifying solutions primarily based on open-source libraries. The description of each chain component, as well as the identified software solution, is available at the PASSES website³.

2.2.1. Image pre-screening

The first task involves image pre-screening to identify and discard corrupted images and those affected by bad weather conditions. This is achieved by examining metadata associated with each image file, including image size and pixel resolution. This initial check helps us detect data corruption and issues related to server accessibility. Additional

Figure 2: Camera views in the three selected sites contributing to the Svalbard camera network. While the Snow pilot site in Hornsund started to acquire images in summer 2023, the other sites will be installed and activated in 2024.

³ <https://passes.cnr.it/Algorithm.html>

analysis of RGB values and image patterns supports identification of scenes with low illumination or intense cloud cover. An additional filter is used to remove any image with lens interferences, such as raindrops or ice crusts.

2.2.2. Image radial distortion correction

Image radial distortion is a major issue associated with sensor specifications. The removal of such distortion requires calibration of the time-lapse camera using a reference chessboard. This procedure involves capturing at least six images of the chessboard at close range from the camera, with different orientations. The ultimate goal of this task is to determine intrinsic lens features for correcting lens distortion.

2.2.3. Image orthorectification

Geometrical projection requires information about the camera orientation and sensor specifications. The orthorectification process corrects the perspective view using methods outlined by Corripio (2004), and it relies on a digital elevation model. Ground control points are essential for assessing the accuracy of this correction.

2.2.4. Image segmentation

Image segmentation is based on the spectral similarity approach, as proposed by Salzano et al. (2019). This module measures spectral variations in a 3D colour space, where the reference endmembers are the theoretical "white" snow and a theoretical "black" target. Parameters estimated in this vector system include the spectral angle, and the Euclidean distance, calculated with respect to references. While spectral similarity is an independent spectral feature, the Euclidean distance of the vector is brightness-dependent. Considering all three-colour components allows for discriminating between snow, shadowed snow, and non-snow areas. Pixel density helps in delineating cluster limits, which are determined based on frequency distribution and Mahalanobis distance.

2.2.5. Image classification

Classification of surface types (snow, non-snow, and shadowed snow) depends on a set of rules that describe a decision tree (Salzano et al. 2019). This tree examines frequency distributions of pixels in the new spectral space, evaluates homogeneity of reflective behaviour, and assesses cluster fragmentation.

2.2.6. Data service prototype

The data service prototype operates in two modes: near-real time and full analysis. In the near-real time option⁴, users can select and view camera system images in RGB format. This mode provides rapid processing without the need for projection and offers an estimated snow cover fraction. The snow cover identification is based on an automated linear classifier that relies on thresholding of the blue channel (BT), as introduced by Salvatori et al. (2011). This method involves counting the frequency of the blue component and defines the snow-not-snow boundary by examining increments in the blue-channel histogram. However, it is important to note that this method has limitations and may be affected by factors such as lighting conditions, surface roughness, and camera distance, which can impact its accuracy in snow cover estimation.

The second mode generates a yearly data product by combining the classification output with the ortho-projection procedure. This delivered product pertains to the fractional snow-covered area (FSCA) and is presented as a grid. The grid is derived from specific satellite products, including Sentinel-2, Landsat 8, or MODIS. The data format adheres to the NetCDF standard format, with metadata defined in accordance with the ISO 19115 guidelines and the Climate & Forecast convention.

2.3. The contribution for assessing the impact of extreme events on the snow cover

The availability of highly time-resolved datasets on seasonal snow cover is crucial for comprehensively

⁴ <https://passes.cnr.it/Classification.html>

Figure 3: Comparison between snow-off day estimations obtained by satellite observations (Sentinel-2 and MODIS), and by terrestrial photography with the CCT instrument footprint (about 20 m) and the Zeppelin webcam over Ny-Ålesund in 2022. Data for terrestrial photography and Sentinel-2 are from Salzano et al. (2023), those related to the MODIS sensor were obtained from Vickers et al. (2020).

assessing the evolution of the Arctic ecosystem, as it allows us to combine data from various spatial and temporal scales. In cryospheric studies, a key metric for understanding the snow season is the end of the melting season, which can be determined using various EO data sources. Satellite data offer reliable observations but come with specific limitations depending on the spaceborne platform. Instruments like MODIS on the Terra and Aqua platforms provide medium spatial resolution (ranging from 250–500 metres) and offer daily overpasses, with the main limitation being occasional cloud cover in Svalbard. On the other hand, platforms like Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8–9 provide higher spatial resolution (around 10–30 metres), allowing for more detailed surface cover descriptions. However, their revisiting time is less frequent, and they are susceptible to cloud cover interference. From this perspective, terrestrial photography plays a significant role in continuously describing surface conditions. It serves as a ground-truth reference, offering a more reliable spatial representation when compared to data from in-situ automated stations (Figure 3).

The contribution of novel EO infrastructures is expected to play an increasingly vital role in

coming years, as phenomena associated with climate change in the Arctic emerge. One such phenomenon is the rising frequency and intensity of warm spells, even at high latitudes. These extreme events involve the recurrent influx of wet and warm air masses into Arctic coastal regions, leading to periods of unpredictable and prolonged warmth in the lower atmosphere. These warm spells can also bring about liquid precipitation, leading to what is known as "rain-on-snow" events. What makes warm spells particularly concerning is their occurrence during the winter season before the snow melting season begins. A case study from Ny-Ålesund illustrates this scenario (Salzano et al. 2023). A rain-on-snow event on March 16, 2022 resulted in the first significant reduction in snow cover and the release of a significant amount of water in late March (see Figure 4). Automated stations recorded that this initial warming event did not lead to a significant reduction in snow water equivalent (SWE), indicating that, at least in flat areas, only moisture and ripening processes occurred within the snowpack. Subsequent solid precipitation events continued until mid-May when another warm spell impacted the area, marking the onset of the actual melting season. By the end of the melting season, the SWE content had completely

Figure 4: Evolution of snow cover extent (SCE) obtained by terrestrial photography in Ny-Ålesund in 2022. While surface reflectance (SR) and snow water equivalent (SWE) were observed by an automated station located close to the Amundsen-Nobile Climate Change Tower (Salzano et al. 2023), the wet snow fraction (WSF) was retrieved by microwave remote sensing (Vickers et al. 2022). Warm spells (WS) are marked with vertical blue areas.

diminished, indicating widespread melting across the area. The optical properties of the surface snow remained relatively stable, with high spectral reflectance (SR), until early May. Minor fluctuations in spectral components occurred before this time, typically associated with fresh snowfall and wind transport. From May onwards, a gradual reduction in both visible and near-infrared spectral reflectance was observed due to ongoing snow melt.

The evolution of SWE and SR closely aligned with observations from terrestrial photography, providing insights into the timing of snow melting at various spatial scales. Considering the footprint of sensors, limited to a 20-metre radius from the observation platforms where automated stations were deployed, both SWE and Snow Cover Extent (SCE) indicated that the snow melting period was essentially complete by June 15th. Results obtained from both satellite and terrestrial platforms, looking at the entire catchment area, showed the snow

cover was essentially gone on June 21, six days later. It is worth noting that satellite data provided more detailed surface information compared to terrestrial photography. Spaceborne platforms are equipped with highly efficient multi-spectral sensors, particularly suited for distinguishing between different surface types, especially in the near-infrared wavelength domain. For further insights into the observed dynamics, microwave sensors, as described by Vickers et al. (2022), were employed. These sensors allowed measurement of the Wet Snow Fraction (WSF), confirming the impact of warm spells during the snow season. The first event was characterised by a significant temperature decrease in the following days, coupled with significant wind, surface water refreezing, and the formation of an ice crust over the snow cover. The second event completed the melting process, resulting in the complete disappearance of the snow cover.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The presented chapter completes the description of terrestrial photography applications on the snow cover. The presented data chain is a flexible tool for processing data from different sensors. The near-real-time processing will be active in 2024 thanks to the Snow Pilot project. Guidelines about calibrating cameras are available on the PASSES webpage⁵. The presented infrastructure will support cryospheric studies and remote sensing applications, but several contributions to other disciplines are already feasible.

The description of snow seasonality will contribute to studies about Arctic ecosystems, providing metrics suitable for assessing the state of permafrost and vegetation. Atmospheric studies will gain information on the occurrence and impact of phenomena such as warm spells and rain-on-snow events. Finally, data integration will surely be involved in studies about surface hydrology, providing solutions for assessing the evolution of the surface drainage system.

4. Unanswered questions

PASSES has matured considerably since 2020 and will soon provide the scientific community working in Svalbard with versatile infrastructure that serves various purposes. The network will be completed in 2024 once various safety and permission issues have been solved. The camera in Hornsund is active since summer 2023, the remaining in

Adventdalen and Bayelva will be installed in winter-spring 2024. This update underscores the crucial role of integrating terrestrial photography with satellite remote sensing. While the potential for cryospheric studies is evident, further integration of the infrastructure would also open new avenues for vegetation studies.

5. Recommendations for the future

Terrestrial photography offers many opportunities for research on snow cover and related topics, but several problems and knowledge gaps limit its full use. We suggest the following actions that the SIOS community can take to support research in this field:

1. Promote projects that use time-lapse cameras, especially in the more remote areas of Svalbard. Use fog and edge computing to enable the use of IoT systems, aiming to overcome data transfer limitations.
2. Support the maintenance of the Svalbard camera system network with a multi-sensor data service for processing images captured for snow cover applications.
3. Foster the integration of terrestrial photography with satellite remote sensing by developing machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques.
4. Encourage the use of time-lapse cameras across disciplines where high-resolution temporal information can be useful for various purposes, including glaciology, hydrology, plant and animal ecology, coastal processes, sea ice tracking, and satellite imagery calibration and validation (Cal/Val).

⁵ <https://passes.cnr.it/Calibration.html>

6. Data availability

Dataset	Parameter	Period	Location	Metadata access (URL)	Dataset provider
Survey about time-lapse cameras applications on snow in Svalbard	Time-lapse cameras	1980–2023	Svalbard	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/9511477e-82d0-4ad2-a0f1-5d01792058ef	IADC
Fractional Snow-Covered Area (FSCA) in Ny-Ålesund	FSCA	2022	Ny-Ålesund	https://metadata.iadc.cnr.it/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/8ca8d01c-2e4d-4e1d-bf7c-450a58a9da63	IADC

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The drainage system in the Bayelva catchment (a) after the extreme event in Ny-Ålesund on March 2022 (Worldview image acquired on 3 April 2022). (b) The same condition viewed from the Amundsen-Nobile Climate Change Tower (CCT) on 3 April 2022. (Photo: Roberto Salzano)